

Recognising and rewarding Open Science

Embedding Open Science criteria within institutional assessment,
hiring and promotion policies and procedures

Call for proposals

2024

OPEN
SCIENCE
NL

Content

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Available budget	1
1.3	Submission deadline(s)	1
2	Aim	2
2.1	Aim of the programme	2
3	Conditions for applicants	3
3.1	Who can apply	3
3.2	What can be applied for	3
3.3	Preparing an application	4
3.4	Conditions for submission	4
3.5	Conditions on granting	5
4	Assessment procedure	6
4.1	The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)	6
4.2	Procedure	6
4.3	Criteria	8
5	Obligations for grant recipients	9
6	Contact and other information	10
6.1	Contact	10
6.2	Other information	10
7	Annex(es):	11
7.1	Explanation of budget module for personnel costs	11

1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the “Recognising and rewarding Open Science” funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO).

In this Call for proposals you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm. A budget of €20M a year is available until 2031. Open Science NL was set up to take responsibility for the allocation of these funds.

This Call falls within the first work programme of Open Science NL, which covers the years 2024-2025. The instruments within this work programme cover the following priority areas:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

This work programme addresses a comprehensive set of needs and range of areas relating to open science, and provides a strong basis from which the uptake of open science practices can continue to grow and flourish in the Netherlands.

The Call for proposals “Recognising and rewarding Open Science” falls under the priority area “empowering communities”. Communities fulfil an essential role in putting open science into practice. Communities consist of researchers, research support staff, policy officers and other experts who meet – often bottom up – to exchange experiences and ensure open science practices become standard. Strengthening, supporting, recognising and rewarding open science activities of these communities or their individual members is therefore a priority.

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is €1,200,000. Within this Call for proposals it is expected that a maximum of 24 proposals will be awarded funding.

1.3 Submission deadline(s)

The deadline for submitting full proposals is **10 September 2024**, before 14:00:00 CET.

When you submit your application in ISAAC, you will also need to enter some details online. Therefore please start submitting your application at least one day before the deadline of this Call for proposals. Applications that are submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration.

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme.

2.1 Aim of the programme

The transition to open science requires a cultural shift which cannot rely solely on the motivation of individual researchers.¹ If open is to become the new normal, it is essential that researchers are recognised and rewarded for putting open science into practice. For research performing organisations, this means including open science in hiring, evaluation and promotion policies. For funders, it means including open science practices in the evaluation of research proposals. In particular, the inclusion of criteria related to open science in the hiring, promotion and tenure policies of institutions is urgently needed. At the international level, the COARA initiative² is taking concrete steps to reform research assessment. Nationally, universities, university medical centres and research institutes committed to embedding open science practices within their policies as part of the national roadmap “Room for Everyone's Talent in Practice” (2023).³ Current developments with regards to recognition and rewards in research and open science are also integrated in the Strategy Evaluation Protocol 2021-2027⁴ of Universities of the Netherlands, KNAW- and NWO-institutes.

The purpose of this Call for proposals is to provide all institutions that have signed up to the Dutch Recognition & Rewards programme with a financial incentive to embed open science (including team science) in their own institutional policies. The funding is intended to help institutions develop and implement a concrete plan for embedding open science within the institutional assessment, hiring and promotion policies and procedures for researchers and professional support staff. It is also important that teamwork and recognising and valuing team science are included in these policies. The funding is intended to facilitate the connections between existing experts within the institution (such as HR advisors, open science experts, researchers, policy officers etc.). Institutions are expected - in line with the national roadmap Room for Everyone's Talent in Practice - to participate in national coordination activities (participation in workshops and events aimed at exchanging good practices and aligning policies, procedures and evaluation criteria at the national level).

¹ Blog post by Brian Nosek “Strategy for Culture Change”: <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>.

² Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment: <https://coara.eu/>

³ <https://recognitionrewards.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Room-for-everyones-talent-in-practice-Road-map-Recognition-Rewards.pdf>

⁴ Strategy Evaluation Protocol: <https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/onderwerpen/onderzoek/evaluatie-protocol-onderzoek-sep>

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

This Call for proposals is aimed at the institutions that signed the Dutch “Recognition & Rewards” programme⁵. Applications can be submitted by the boards of the following institutions:

- universities located in the Kingdom of the Netherlands;
- university medical centres;
- institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO.

Extra conditions:

- Applications are submitted by the board of the institution
- For the institutes affiliated with the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO, the overarching institutional board can submit a proposal (one for the KNAW institutes and one for the NWO institutes).
- The philosophical universities, as described in the *Wet op het hoger onderwijs en wetenschappelijk onderzoek*, point i, can also submit one proposal where one of the institutions will act as the main applicant.
- There is a maximum of one application per institution.

3.2 What can be applied for

For an application in this Call for proposals, a maximum of €50,000 can be applied for in total. The maximum duration of the proposed project is one year.

Apart from the costs that cannot be applied for (as listed below), there are few restrictions to the budget for the applications. Eligible for funding are, for example, personnel costs for a short period of time, material costs, organisational costs for conferences and workshops, knowledge utilisation (of results) and travel costs (second class) to stimulate collaboration/knowledge exchange.

Costs that cannot be applied for are:

- costs already covered by grants awarded to the main applicant or other project members;
- - basic facilities within the institution (e.g. laptops, office furniture, etc.);
- - maintenance and insurance costs;
- - overhead expenses.

The costs must be justified in the proposal and outlined in the budget form. The grant will be awarded as a lump sum. You should only apply for funding that is essential to realise the project.

A more detailed explanation of the budget module for personnel costs can be found in the annex to this Call for proposals (7.1).

⁵ <https://recognitionrewards.nl/about/stakeholders/>

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Compulsory annex:

- budget

The appendix must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by NWO. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application. The budget must be submitted in ISAAC as an Excel file. All of the other annexes, except for the budget, must be submitted as PDF files (without encryption). Any annexes other than those stated above are not permitted.

You must write your application in Dutch or English.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration.

As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by NWO.

For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

Does a main and/or co-applicant work at an organisation that is not included in the ISAAC database? You can report this via relatiebeheer@nwo.nl so that the organisation can be added. This will take several days. It is therefore important that you report this at least one week before the deadline.

Applicants are expected to have informed the organisation where they work about submitting the application and that the organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

NWO will assess your application against the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, NWO requests you to be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the main applicant meets the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;

- the application form is, after a possible request to make additions or changes, complete and filled out according to the instructions;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in Dutch or English;
- the application budget is drawn up in accordance with the conditions for this Call for proposals;
- the proposed project has a duration of at most one year;
- all of the required annexes are, after a possible request to make additions or changes, complete and filled out according to the instructions.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The NWO Grant Rules 2017, except where this Call for proposals deviates from the standard, and the Agreement on the Payment of Costs for Scientific Research are applicable to all applications⁶.

3.5.1 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules 2017, the project that NWO funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by NWO, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/scientific-integrity>.

3.5.2 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or licence.

3.5.3 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol: <https://www.absfocalpoint.nl/en/absfocalpoint.htm>. NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

⁶ The most recent HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates at the time of the deadline will be applied in all awarded grants in this Call for proposals

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the Open Science NL office will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)).

4.1 The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research institutions, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than on the basis of surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

NWO strives not to rely on indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor or the h-index when assessing applications. Applicants are not allowed to mention these in their applications. You are, however, allowed to list other scientific products besides publications, such as datasets, patents, software and code, et cetera.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility of the proposal;
- assessment;
- rebuttal;
- decision-making.

Due to the expertise present in the Open Science NL office and the small size of the grant, NWO has decided with regard to the assessment of these applications to exercise the option to assess all applications without involving referees and external committee.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from NWO whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. NWO will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). NWO can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, NWO may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Assessment

Proposals will be assessed by the Open Science NL office based on the criteria set out below (4.3). The applications in this round are of a non-competitive nature, and Open Science NL strives to award all applications that meet at least 'good' on the conditions and criteria as stated in Section 4.3. For more information on the qualifications, see [Applying for funding, how does it work? | NWO](#)

4.2.4 Rebuttal

The main applicant subsequently receives the advice of the Open Science NL office. You then have the opportunity to formulate a rebuttal. You will be given five working days to submit your rebuttal via ISAAC. If you decide to withdraw the proposal, then you should do this as quickly as possible by sending an email stating this to the office and withdrawing the proposal in ISAAC. If NWO receives your rebuttal after the deadline, then it will not be included in the rest of the procedure.

4.2.5 Decision-making

Finally, the Open Science NL Steering Board will assess the procedure followed as well as the advice from the assessment committee. They will subsequently determine the final qualifications and make a decision over awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.6 Timetable

Below, you will find the timetable for this Call for proposals. During the current procedure, NWO might find it necessary to make further changes to the timetable for this Call for proposals. You will be informed about this in time.

Proposals	
10 September 2024 before 14:00 CEST	Deadline proposals
October 2024	Advice Open Science NL office
October 2024	Applicants can submit a rebuttal
November/December 2024	Decision by Open Science NL Steering Board

4.3 Criteria

4.3.1 Substantive assessment criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be substantially assessed on the basis of the following criteria:

1. Alignment with the scope of the Call (30%)
2. Feasibility of the proposal (50%)
 - a. How realistic is the project plan;
 - b. Is there enough expertise within the project team to successfully execute the project? The team should have the necessary skills and expertise to support a successful outcome of the project.
 - c. Is there an analysis of risk factors and an adequate risk mitigation strategy?
 - d. Is the budget reasonable for the proposed work and sufficiently substantiated?
3. Sustainability of the plans (20%)
 - a. Are the plans for long-term embedding of the project (outcomes) within the institutional policies sufficiently addressed?

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1 Socially responsible licensing

The knowledge that emerges from the project could be suitable for use in society. When agreements about licensing and/or the transfer of research results developed under this Call for proposals are made, due consideration should be given to the ten principles for socially responsible licensing, as stated in the NFU factsheet "[19.4511_Ten_principles_for_Socially_Responsible_Licensing_v19-12-2019.pdf \(nfu.nl\)](#)".

5.2 Open Access

As a signatory to the Berlin Declaration (2003) and a member of cOAlition S (2018), NWO is committed to making the results of the research it funds openly accessible (Open Access). By doing this, NWO supports the ambitions of the Dutch government to make all publicly funded research available Open Access. Scientific publications arising from projects awarded on the basis of this Call for proposals must therefore be made available in Open Access form in accordance with the NWO Open Access Policy. For more detailed information about NWO's Open Access policy, see [Open Science | NWO](#).

Other outputs resulting from this Call for Proposals, such as presentations, reports, training materials, working papers and posters also need to be shared as openly as possible, under an open licence. It is advised that these outputs are shared via a trusted repository, as registered on [OpenDOAR⁷](#).

⁷ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opensoar/>

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For specific questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Dr. Marta Teperek, programme leader FAIR data, Open Science NL
ewvanopenscience@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Other information

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

NWO processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

NWO might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annex(es):

7.1 Explanation of budget module for personnel costs

This explanation is specifically generated for the “Recognising and rewarding of Open Science” Call for proposals. The conditions described in this annex only apply to this specific Call for proposals.

Staff positions eligible for funding	Maximum amount
Scientific or non-scientific	In accordance with the <i>Handleiding Overheidstarieven</i> [HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates] ⁸

It is possible to apply for the funding of the salary costs of personnel who make a substantial contribution to the project.

- For universities, medical university medical centres, institutes affiliated with the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO and other institutes, salary costs will be funded based on the collective labour agreement pay scale of the employee concerned in accordance with the applicable rate at the time of awarding the grant as taken from Table 2.1, column ‘Hourly rate productive hours, excl. Dutch VAT’ from the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates] ([Salary tables | NWO](#)).

⁸ The most recent HOT- Manual Dutch Government Rates at the time of the deadline will be applied in all awarded grants in this Call for proposals

Publication: May 2024

Dutch Research Council

Visiting address:

Location The Hague

Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië

2593 CE The Hague

Netherlands

Location Utrecht

Winthontlaan 2

3526 KV Utrecht

Cover image: credits Shutterstock

[Dutch Research Council | NWO](#)

[Open Science NL](#)

